

POLYSEMY OF THE LEXEME "SUCCESS" IN THE LEXICAL FIELD

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Azimova Muazzam

scientific-investigator of Foreign languages department of Bukhara Engineering
Technology Institute (Uzbekistan)

Abstract:

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About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

To analyze all the meanings of lexical units included in the field "Success", and highlighting the main types of polysemy, the interpretations in the dictionaries of the English language that were used. When searching for interpretations of the studied lexemes, the most accurate definitions were found in the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary (OALD) and Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English (LDOCE). It was also discovered that OALD includes some lexeme values that were not found in other dictionaries.

When analyzing the meanings of lexical units, polysemantic and single-valued lexemes were identified. Most of all, polysemantic lexemes were found - 30 field units, while the number of single-valued lexemes consisted 14 units. To lexemes in which only one value, include the following: fruit, self-actualization, feat, victory, win, fame, renown, popularity, prestige, bestseller, blockbuster, prosperity, affluence, well-being. Considering the structure of single-valued words, we can conclude that they are simple (feat, victory, win, fame, prestige) and complex lexemes (self-actualization, bestseller, blockbuster, well-being). Derived lexical units most often have several meanings.

The analysis of the meanings of lexical units made it possible to distinguish different types of polysemy: radial, chain and mixed type of polysemy. In addition to these types, there were cases of metonymic and metaphorical polysemy, as well as hidden polysemy.

When analyzing all the meanings of lexical units, it was also found that some values do not match the selected value included in the studied semantic field. This conclusion served as the basis for identifying new types of lexical polysemy in the study of all the meanings of lexemes included in the semantic field. Until now, the term has not been introduced into scientific use to denote polysemantic words, the

meanings of which have a distant semantic relationship with each other and are not included in the same semantic field.

The author of this article proposes to use the term close-range lexical polysemy, which means the values of the lexemes included in the studied semantic field, and the values lexemes that have a meaning close to the main one. As a criterion definition of close-rang lexical polysemy, a component analysis of interpretations was used. If, when analyzing the meanings of lexical units, some semantic components coincided with the components of the main meaning, then we concluded that we were dealing with close-rang lexical polysemy. Also, the meanings of lexemes were compared with the standard interpretation, to which synonyms from the studied semantic field were selected: "success is the achievement of smth. desired, planned or attempted, favorable but unexpected".

Long-range lexical polysemy refers to the meanings of lexical units that go far beyond the field and have a weak semantic connection with the meanings included in this field.

The analysis of lexeme interpretations has shown that some lexemes have only two meanings, and then it is impossible to distinguish a chain, radial or mixed type of polysemy. In this case, it is possible to trace the semantic relationship between the meanings of lexemes and attribute the meanings to near or long-range lexical polysemy.

Let's consider the most interesting examples of lexemes in which there were different types of polysemy are distinguished. Let's analyze examples of chain polysemy, in which the next value follows from the previous one.

For example, the lexeme gain has three meanings. The semantic field under study includes the first value, which refers to the achievement of some benefits or improvements by planning or effort. But it should be noted that there is a hidden polysemy in this meaning, there is a need to distinguish between the concepts of by planning or effort, since achievement through planning or effort are different concepts. From the first value follows the second value "an increase in the amount or level of something", and from the second value comes the third value "financial profit". Financial profit is a narrower concept from the second meaning. All three meanings refer to the close-rang lexical polysemy. In the second meaning, the semantic component an increase in the amount or level of something has a relationship with the semantic component advantage or improvement. In the third sense, making a profit can also refer to success.

Consider the values of the lexeme miracle. This lexeme has three meanings.

First of all, a miracle means something amazing and mystical, which may not obey the usual laws of nature, but is a consequence of God's grace. The second meaning of "a very successful event that is surprising and unexpected" originates from the first meaning, it means some kind of successful event that is surprising

and unexpected. From this value we get the third value "excellent achievement in a certain field of activity", since an amazing achievement in a certain field can be the result, among other things, of concomitant luck. In all three meanings there are such semantic components as an unusual event, a successful event, an amazing and unexpected, an excellent achievement, therefore these meanings belong to the close-rang lexical polysemy.

The lexeme welfare has three meanings. The first value is "the general health, happiness and safety of a person, an animal or a group" refers to the semantic field under study, but hidden polysemy is found in it. The lexeme safety in this definition most likely means "necessary prosperity for life". But prosperity is not always accompanied by happiness or health, so it makes sense to separate these concepts. The first value is followed by the second value "practical or financial help that is provided, often by the government, for people or animals that need it". The third value is a variation of the second value. In this the interpretation refers to special payments or benefits that are usually provided to unprotected segments of the population: the unemployed, the poor, the sick, etc. The first meaning is a close-rang lexical polysemy, and the second and third meanings refer to a long-range lexical polysemy. These values are related to financial assistance provided by the State to vulnerable segments of the population. These values do not mean making a profit due to their achievements and a decent standard of living, so these values belong to a long-range lexical polysemy.

Next, we will analyze examples of radial polysemy, in which all subsequent values are formed from the original value. For example, the triumph lexeme has three meanings, the first of which refers to the semantic field under study: "an important victory or achievement after a difficult struggle". But there is a hidden polysemy in this interpretation, since triumph can be understood not only as an important victory after difficult overcoming, but also as a significant achievement. On this basis, the first interpretation was divided into two definitions, and the triumph lexeme has entered into two different synonymous series. The second meaning follows from the first definition, which refers to the feeling of satisfaction from victory or achievement. In the third meaning, we are talking about a successful example of something that also follows from the first meaning. All three meanings refer to the close-rang lexical polysemy.

In the lexeme glory we find a semantic connection between the meanings of lexical units. The first meaning is "praise and thanks, especially as given to God" can be considered the most general, since in this meaning we are talking about praise or gratitude in general, and especially in relation to God. The second value indicates an important achievement that is admired and praised. And in the third meaning, "great beauty, or something special or extremely beautiful, that gives great pleasure", it is said about something so beautiful that it causes admiration - in

this case, we can talk about beautiful nature, wonders of the world, etc. In this example, only the second value refers to the close-rang lexical polysemy, and the remaining values refer to the long-range lexical polysemy.

Consider another example of radial polysemy. At the lexeme honor five values were found. The first value is semantically related to the other values and is the widest, all other values come from it. At the same time, several definitions correspond to the first value, since there is a hidden polysemy in it: "the respect that people have for someone who achieves something great, is very powerful, or behaves in a way that is morally right". Respect as a result of achieving something amazing refers to the semantic field under study and it differs in meaning from respect due to the acquisition of power, since power can not always be obtained in an honest way, power can also be inherited, and not acquired through any achievements. In this interpretation, another component of the meaning is respect for someone who is distinguished by highly moral behavior. This component of the value can also be separated from the rest. The second definition of "the belief and practice of someone who has high moral standards" and the fifth definition of "a woman's virginity before being married" are related to the first interpretation in the meaning of high moral behavior. The fifth meaning in the dictionary is designated as outdated, but nevertheless the chastity of girls is still very much appreciated in some countries and is important when getting married. The third and fourth values are also related to the first. A mixed type of polysemy was noted in some lexical units, and some meanings were also found that could rather be attributed to homonyms due to the loss of semantic connection between the meanings. Let's take a closer look at such examples.

For example, the fulfillment lexeme has four meanings. The first meaning "the act of doing or achieving what was hoped for or expected" is followed by the second and third values. The fourth meaning, namely "the act of packing and sending something that a customer has ordered", is represented by only in Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary. This value has a weak semantic connection with the rest of the values. This is an example of radial-chain polysemy. The first three values refer to the close-rang lexical polysemy, and the last value refers to the far lexical polysemy, since this value goes far beyond the field.

Most of the values were found in the leader and hit lexemes, and these values have a complex relationship with each other. Let's take a closer look at the leader lexeme, which has seven values. The first value is "the person who directs or controls a group, organization, country etc" is associated with the second, third and fifth values. The third meaning refers to the product or company that is the best or most successful. From the third value "the product or company that is the best or most successful" there was a transition to the fourth value "a piece of writing in a newspaper giving the paper's opinion on a subject". In the seventh meaning, "a

long thin branch that grows from the stem of a bush or tree beyond other branches” there was a metaphorical transfer from a human leader to a branch that stands out among the rest.

The value of “technical: the part at the beginning of a film or recording tape which has nothing on it” is difficult to correlate with other meanings, so in this case it can be assumed that there will be a transition of polysemy into homonymy. The meanings from the first to the fifth can be attributed to the close-rang lexical polysemy, since the concept of a successful product or a successful person is at the heart of the meanings. In addition to the meaning of "successful product", the meaning of "man-leader" can be attributed to the close-rang lexical polysemy, since the concept of success always correlates with the person who achieves it. Sixth and seventh the meanings belong to a long-rang lexical polysemy and are very different from the rest.

Another lexeme that has a complex organization of relations between values is the lexical unit hit. This word has eight meanings, but not all meanings have a semantic connection. In order to find out which meaning is the main one, it is necessary to consider the origin of this word. The hit lexeme comes from late Old English hittan (in the sense “come upon, find”). It follows from this that the first value is “an act of hitting somebody/something with your hand or with an object held in your hand” it is the main one, the second meaning is semantically connected with it. Complicated to identify how the meaning of "blow, push" turned into the meaning of "popular product", in particular to denote a popular song.

The hit lexeme refers to different areas: music (popular song), information technology (fifth and sixth meanings), the sphere of illegal narcotic drugs (seventh meaning). During the analysis of the values, it can be assumed that some meanings of the word hit have lost semantic connection with each other and after a while it will happen the transition from polysemy to homonymy. In this lexeme, only the third and fourth values refer to the close-rang lexical polysemy, the remaining values are semantically unrelated to the values included in the field.

The analysis of the relations between the meanings of lexemes revealed metaphorical and metonymic polysemy. Some examples have already been considered when analyzing a mixed type of polysemy, where metaphorical and metonymic polysemy met. Let's look at more examples of such relationships. For example, in the lexeme coup we find the metonymic transfer from the first value “a sudden and sometimes violent attempt by citizens or the army to take control of the government” to the second “an achievement that is extremely impressive because it was very difficult”. In this example, you can see the transfer from the action (a sudden and sometimes violent attempt citizens or the army to take power into their own hands) on the result of the action (a very impressive achievement that was achieved with great effort).The second value refers to the semantic field under

study and indicates impressive achievements in general, not necessarily on violent military actions or military coups.

Consider the values of the lexical unit greatness. The first value "importance and fame, power, or success" has a hidden polysemy. In this definition, success is viewed from a position of power, fame, or importance of position. In the semantic field under study, success is viewed from the point of view of fame due to achievements. The first and second values have a semantic relationship based on similarity the impression made: the achievement of greatness and a large number of, the size of something. From the second value "the large amount, size, or degree of something" follows the last value "the very good quality of something". In this lexical unit, the first and third meanings refer to the close-range lexical polysemy. In the third meaning we find the semantic component of the very good quality of smth., which is present in the interpretations of other lexical units included in the semantic field. Consequently, this meaning can also be attributed to the close-rang lexical polysemy. The second meaning refers to long-range lexical polysemy.

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